

Article

General homogenised formulation for thick viscoelastic layered structures for finite element applications

Ondiz Zarraga^{1,*}
and Fernando Cortés¹

¹ Department of Mechanics, Design and Industrial Management. University of Deusto. Avda. de las Universidades 24. 48007 Bilbao. Spain

* Correspondence: ondiz.zarraga@deusto.es

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Abstract: Viscoelastic layered surface treatments are widely used for passive control of vibration and noise, specially in passenger vehicles and buildings. When the viscoelastic layer is thick, the structural models must account for shear effects. In this work a homogenised formulation for thick N-layered viscoelastic structures for finite element applications is presented, which allows to avoid computationally expensive models based on solids. This is achieved by substituting the flexural stiffness in the governing thin beam or plate equation by a frequency dependent equivalent flexural stiffness that takes shear and the properties of the different layers into account. The formulation is applied to Free Layer Damping (FLD) and Constrained Layer Damping (CLD) beams and plates and its ability to accurately compute the eigenpairs and dynamic response is tested by implementing it in a finite element model and comparing the obtained results to those given by the standard for the application — Oberst for the FLD case and RKU for the CLD one — and to a solid model, which is used as reference. For every case, the homogenised formulation is nearly as precise as the model based on solids, but requires less computational effort, and provides better results than the standard model.

Keywords: beam model; plate model; surface treatment; vibration reduction; fractional damping; finite element; homogenisation

1. Introduction

When a structure is subjected to vibration and the emitted sound must be reduced, surface treatments are a handy solution. This kind of passive control is specially used in appliances, building and human transportation [1–3]. In this last case, apart from reducing structure-borne sound [4], this technology serves the purpose of increasing passenger comfort.

Surface treatments are layered slender structures that can be divided into two groups: free layer damping (FLD) and constrained layer damping (CLD). The first consists in a layer of a base material, usually metallic, to which a layer of viscoelastic material is glued either in the form of damping tiles [5] or coating [4]. This way, when the treated structure deforms in bending, the viscoelastic layer suffers an extensional effort and dissipates energy in the form of heat. CLD surface treatments, on the contrary, have an additional constraining layer, usually metallic as well, that forces the viscoelastic core to deform in shear so that energy is dissipated [1]. Even if the CLD configuration is more effective to reduce vibration, FLD treatments continue to be applied due to their easy and relatively economic implementation [6].

In order to analyse the dynamic behaviour of such layered structures several strategies have been proposed, ranging from analytical to numerical methods. The former approach can be followed when

33 dealing with simple structures and damping models but, when the geometry of the structure under
34 study, its boundary conditions or applied forces are complex, analytical models fall short and finite
35 element models are the common choice. Two paths can be followed if solid finite element models, that
36 are demanding in terms of computational resources [7], are to be avoided: to propose a homogenised
37 formulation that takes into account the contribution of every layer so that traditional plate elements can
38 be used; or to develop a specific finite element model for layered structures. In the engineering practise
39 it is also common to use the multilayer elements available in commercial finite element software, but
40 they do not allow the introduction of complex damping models, that are often needed when dealing
41 with this kind of surface treatments.

42 Models can be divided according to the technology for which they have been developed.
43 Regarding the FLD case, homogenised formulations have been commonly proposed, starting from the
44 Oberst model [8], in which an equivalent flexural stiffness for the two layers is proposed and up to the
45 more recent [6], in which a model of a cantilever plate was developed with the aim of studying the
46 frequency dependence of the response. Neither of these homogenised models considered the effect of
47 shear and are thus limited to thin plates where this effect can be neglected.

48 As for CLD structures, the first works aiming to understand their dynamic behaviour are the ones
49 by Ross [9], Kerwin [10] and Ungar [11] that resulted in the RKU method that is still nowadays the
50 standard in the field. This method defines an equivalent flexural stiffness that links the shear strain in
51 the damping layer to the bending motion of the plate. The analytical procedure has been followed
52 in subsequent works such as [12], in which the work by Ross, Kerwin and Ungar was extended or,
53 after, in [13] in which a model for thick layered structures that considers nine degrees of freedom
54 (DOF) is presented. This last work is stated as a general case and can degenerate into one- or two-
55 layered structures so it can be also applied to FLD structures. Due to the complexity of the analytical
56 modelling, these models are limited to simple geometries.

57 Also, in [14] a homogenised formulation similar to those for modelling FLD structures is presented.
58 Thin plate elements that consider the properties of the three layers are proposed but, as shear is not
59 considered, it is only valid when the viscoelastic core is thin.

60 With the idea of dealing with complex geometries, applied forces or boundary conditions, different
61 finite element models have been proposed. For example, in [15] an 8 DOF beam element is presented;
62 in [16] triangular and rectangular sandwich elements with seven DOF in each node are developed;
63 in [17] a three-layer four-node rectangular element with 7 DOF on every node is used; or in [18] a
64 nine-node isoparametric 2D element is proposed to model the behaviour of active-passive composite
65 beams. The finite element method is also used, but with a different approach, in the series [19,20]
66 where the viscoelastic core of a CLD structure is modelled as a thick beam or plate, depending of
67 the structure under study, and the metallic layers are represented as thin beams or plates. The main
68 drawback of these methods is the need of developing a specific finite element formulation for the
69 application, instead of taking advantage of the solutions already available.

70 In view of the above, this work presents a general homogenised formulation for the dynamic
71 analysis of thick viscoelastic layered beams and plates that extends the previous models proposed by
72 the authors [21–24] to N-layered structures. The formulation uses conventional beam and plate finite
73 elements and introduces the effect of shear by means of a frequency dependent equivalent flexural
74 stiffness. With this aim, first, the formulation for a general one- or two-dimensional surface treatment
75 with any number of layers is presented; then, the method is implemented in a finite element model and
76 applied to FLD and CLD beams and plates for which the eigenpairs, i.e. eigenvalues and eigenvectors,
77 and the dynamic response to an external force are computed; finally, the obtained results are compared
78 to the ones provided by a three-dimensional finite element model and to the standard model in the
79 field: the Oberst model for FLD structures and the RKU for those with a CLD configuration. For every
80 case, the dynamic behaviour of the viscoelastic layer is represented by a four parameter fractional
81 derivative model.

2. General formulation for viscoelastic layered surface treatments

In order to develop a general formulation, the N-layered beam shown in Figure 1 is considered. The process goes as follows: first, an equivalent modulus that takes into account the contribution of the different materials to the overall stiffness of the beam is computed; then, the effect of shear is introduced by a frequency dependent term that modifies this equivalent modulus. The formulation for layered beams will be presented and, afterwards, it is extended to plates.

Figure 1. N-layered beam, H_i , h_n , L and b stand for the thickness of the i th layer, the position of the neutral fibre, the length of the beam and its width, respectively.

Following the classical theory for layered beams, the total flexural stiffness B_{eq} for a N-layered beam can be expressed as the sum of the flexural stiffness of its layers as

$$B_{\text{eq}} = \sum_{i=1}^N B_i = \sum_{i=1}^N E_i I_i, \quad (1)$$

where E_i stands for the elastic modulus of the material of the i th layer and I_i for the cross-sectional inertia moment computed from the neutral axis. This inertia term is obtained for the i th layer from the integral

$$I_i = b \int_{h_{i-1}}^{h_i} y^2 dy, \quad (2)$$

where b is the width of the beam, that is supposed to be constant, and defining the integration limits

$$\begin{aligned} h_0 &= -h_n \\ h_1 &= -h_n + H_1 \\ &\dots \\ h_i &= -h_n + H_1 + \dots + H_i \\ &\dots \\ h_N &= -h_n + H_1 + \dots + H_N, \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

for every layer, where h_n stands for the position of the neutral fibre that is located in

$$h_n = \frac{E_1 H_1 \frac{H_1}{2} + E_2 H_2 \left(H_1 + \frac{H_2}{2} \right) + \dots + E_N H_N \left(H_1 + H_2 + \dots + \frac{H_N}{2} \right)}{\sum_{i=1}^N E_i H_i}. \quad (4)$$

If the small deformation hypothesis holds, it is possible to uncouple the transverse displacement due to bending $v_M(x, t)$ and to shear $v_Q(x, t)$ as

$$v(x, t) = v_M(x, t) + v_Q(x, t). \quad (5)$$

97 The first term, as it is originated by the bending moment $M(x, t)$, satisfies

$$M(x, t) = B_{\text{eq}} \frac{\partial^2 v_M(x, t)}{\partial x^2}, \quad (6)$$

98 where B_{eq} is the equivalent flexural stiffness from (1).

99 Likewise, the second term is related to the shear force $Q(x, t)$ by

$$Q(x, t) = K_{\text{eq}} \frac{\partial v_Q(x, t)}{\partial x}, \quad (7)$$

100 where the total shear stiffness K_{eq} is obtained by combining the shear stiffnesses of all layers

$$\frac{1}{K_{\text{eq}}} = \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{1}{K_i}. \quad (8)$$

101 If a second order shear stress law is considered, the shear stiffness for the i th layer follows

$$\frac{1}{K_i} = \frac{1}{B_{\text{eq}}^2 b} \int_{h_{i-1}}^{h_i} \frac{\Gamma_i(y)^2}{G_i} dy, \quad (9)$$

102 where, G_i is the shear modulus of the material of the i th layer and

$$\Gamma(y) = \int_{S'} y E(y) dS', \quad (10)$$

103 where S' represents the area above a point $P(x, y)$ (see a book on mechanics of materials for the details,
104 e.g. [25]).

105 Taking into account the integration limits defined in (3), $\Gamma_i(y)$ has the value

$$\Gamma_1(y) = \frac{E_1 b (h_0^2 - y^2)}{2} \quad (11)$$

106 for the bottom layer,

$$\Gamma_i(y) = \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} \frac{E_j b (h_{j-1}^2 - h_j^2)}{2} + \frac{E_i b (h_{i-1}^2 - y^2)}{2} \quad (12)$$

107 for the middle layers 2 to $N-1$ and

$$\Gamma_N(y) = \frac{E_N b (h_N^2 - y^2)}{2} \quad (13)$$

108 for the top layer N .

109 The equivalent flexural and shear stiffnesses B_{eq} and K_{eq} are then introduced in the Timoshenko
110 thick beam formulation in order to account for the effect of the different materials of the layers,
111 resulting in

$$\frac{B_{\text{eq}}}{\rho_L} \frac{\partial^4 v(x, t)}{\partial x^4} - \frac{B_{\text{eq}}}{K_{\text{eq}}} \frac{\partial^4 v(x, t)}{\partial x^2 \partial t^2} + \frac{\partial^2 v(x, t)}{\partial t^2} = q(x, t), \quad (14)$$

112 if the terms related to the rotational inertia of the cross section are ignored, and where $q(x, t)$ stands
113 for the distributed force per unit length applied to the beam and $\rho_L = \sum_{i=1}^N \rho_i A_i$ being the mass per
114 unit length and ρ_i and A_i the density and area of the cross section of the i th layer.

115 Supposing harmonic response both in space and time

$$v(x, t) = A \exp [i(\beta x - \omega t)] \quad (15)$$

116 where A , β and ω are the amplitude, wave number and natural frequency. After some manipulation,
117 an equation equivalent to the Euler–Bernouilli thin beam formula but which includes the effect of
118 shear can be obtained

$$\frac{\tilde{B}(t)}{\rho_L} \frac{\partial^4 v(x, t)}{\partial x^4} + \frac{\partial^2 v(x, t)}{\partial t^2} = q(x, t) \quad (16)$$

119 where $\tilde{B}(t)$ is the time domain counterpart of the flexural stiffness modulus that, in the frequency
120 domain, takes the form

$$B(\omega) = \frac{B_{\text{eq}}}{\left(\varphi(\omega) + \sqrt{\varphi(\omega)^2 + 1}\right)^2}, \quad (17)$$

121 in which

$$\varphi(\omega) = \frac{\omega \sqrt{B_{\text{eq}} \rho_L}}{2K_{\text{eq}}}. \quad (18)$$

122 Two considerations should be made regarding this final expression: the first is that if the modulus
123 of the material of any of the layers is complex, the formulation is still valid, the flexural stiffness
124 terms becoming complex; the second is that, even if the dependence to frequency could be thought
125 as a unnecessary addition of complexity, most times the viscoelastic materials used in this kind of
126 applications already show frequency dependent properties.

127 It should be also noted that the presented formulation only accounts for the bending behaviour
128 of the structure under study and that is only valid for the dynamic regime i.e. it cannot be used to
129 compute the static response of thick beams in which the shear is relevant. Considering that the domain
130 of application is the reduction of noise and vibration, this does not pose a problem.

131 In order to extend the formulation to plates, the mass per unit length ρ_L should be substituted by
132 the mass per unit area

$$\rho_S = \sum_{i=1}^N \rho_i H_i, \quad (19)$$

133 where ρ_i and H_i stand for the density and thickness of the i th layer. Also, when dealing with bending,
134 the equivalent flexural stiffness B_{eq} should be substituted by its counterpart for plates

$$D_{\text{eq}} = \sum_{i=1}^N \int_{h_{i-1}}^{h_i} \frac{E_i}{3(1-\nu_i^2)} z^2 dz \quad (20)$$

135 E_i and ν_i being the elastic modulus and Poisson's ratio of the i th layer. The integration limits are the
136 same ones defined for beams in (3). The shear formula still holds taking into account that, for plates,
137 the shear force is considered per unit width and, then, $b = 1$ in (9) and (11)-(13).

138 This way, the frequency dependent flexural stiffness is given by

$$D(\omega) = \frac{D_{\text{eq}}}{\left(\varphi(\omega) + \sqrt{\varphi(\omega)^2 + 1}\right)^2} \quad (21)$$

139 where $\varphi(\omega)$ follows the expression

$$\varphi(\omega) = \frac{\omega \sqrt{D_{\text{eq}} \rho_S}}{2K_{\text{eq}}}. \quad (22)$$

140 Considering also for plates y the vertical axis and v the transverse displacement in order to avoid
 141 the confusion between the typically used w and the natural frequency ω , the Kirchhoff–Love thin plate
 142 equation becomes

$$\tilde{D}(t) \left(\frac{\partial^4 v(x, z, t)}{\partial x^4} + 2 \frac{\partial^4 v(x, z, t)}{\partial x^2 \partial z^2} + \frac{\partial^4 v(x, z, t)}{\partial z^4} \right) + \rho_S \frac{\partial^2 v(x, z, t)}{\partial t^2} = p(x, z, t) \quad (23)$$

143 where $p(x, z, t)$ is the distributed force per unit area applied to the plate and $\tilde{D}(t)$ stands for the
 144 flexural stiffness in the time domain and introduces the effect of shear into the formulation. The same
 145 considerations already mentioned for the beams apply here: the presented procedure is only applicable
 146 when working in the frequency domain.

147 3. Dynamic analysis

148 The presented homogenised formulation is used to compute, first, the natural frequencies and
 149 mode shapes of layered beams and plates and, later, their response in the frequency domain. To this
 150 aim, the finite element method is used. As the formulation is directly based on the thin beam (or plate)
 151 equation, standard elements can be used, the single difference being that the stiffness matrix is, in this
 152 case, frequency dependent.

153 This fact does not add much complexity taking into account that, due to its definition, the
 154 formulation allows to compute the frequency dependent stiffness from the static stiffness matrix $\mathbf{K}(0)$
 155 as

$$\mathbf{K}_{\text{beam}}^*(\omega) = \frac{B^*(\omega)}{B(0)} \mathbf{K}(0) \quad (24)$$

156 for beams and,

$$\mathbf{K}_{\text{plate}}^*(\omega) = \frac{D^*(\omega)}{D(0)} \mathbf{K}(0) \quad (25)$$

157 for plates. This implies that an external program can be used to produce the mesh for the structure,
 158 which drastically simplifies the computation process. It is also worth mentioning that, in a general
 159 case, the frequency dependent stiffness matrix can be complex — that is the reason why it is marked
 160 with an asterisk, in a fashion that will be followed all along the work.

161 This said, the process for computing, on the one hand, natural frequencies and mode shapes and,
 162 on the other, the dynamic response is referred.

163 3.1. Natural frequencies and mode shapes

164 For both beam and plates, the eigenpairs of the system satisfy

$$(-\lambda_r^* \mathbf{M} + \mathbf{K}^*(\omega_r)) \boldsymbol{\Phi}_r^* = \mathbf{0} \quad (26)$$

165 where \mathbf{M} is the mass matrix, $\omega_r = \text{Re}(\sqrt{\lambda_r^*})$ is the natural frequency for mode r th and λ_r^* and $\boldsymbol{\Phi}_r^*$
 166 are the corresponding eigenvalue and eigenvector. As the stiffness matrix is frequency dependent, an
 167 iterative method is needed to compute the eigenpairs of the system. For each mode, the computation
 168 starts considering the static stiffness matrix $\mathbf{K}(0)$ and computing the associated natural frequency.
 169 Then, the algorithm shown in Figure 2 is followed, obtaining the natural frequency from the updated
 170 stiffness matrix and comparing it to the one computed in the previous iteration. When the difference
 171 in natural frequency for two subsequent iterations is less than a given tolerance, the process stops.

172 It should be noted that the iterative method can be expensive in terms of computational resources.
 173 In such case, approximate techniques like the one presented in [26] can be applied to reduce the
 174 computational cost.

Figure 2. Algorithm to compute the eigenvalues and eigenvectors of the r th mode.

175 In the case under study, apart from the static case, the eigenvalues of the system are complex due
 176 to the fractional model used to represent the behaviour of the viscoelastic material. If the viscoelastic
 177 layer covers the whole structure the eigenvectors are real, due to the proportionality of damping, but,
 178 in a general case, both eigenvalues and eigenvectors could be complex.

179 Apart from the natural frequencies and mode shapes, also the loss factor is used to compare the
 180 performance of the different models. For the r th mode it follows

$$\eta_r = \frac{\text{Im}(\lambda_r^*)}{\text{Re}(\lambda_r^*)}. \quad (27)$$

181 3.2. Dynamic response

182 The dynamic response of the structure is obtained by solving the motion equation in the frequency
 183 domain

$$\left(-\omega^2 \mathbf{M} + \mathbf{K}^*(\omega)\right) \mathbf{v}^*(\omega) = \mathbf{F}(\omega) \quad (28)$$

184 for the response vector $\mathbf{v}^*(\omega)$.

185 For the computations, a uniform impulse pressure (1 Pa) on the upper surface of the structure is
 186 considered as the force vector $\mathbf{F}(\omega)$ and, for the comparison between models, the RMS value of the
 187 transverse displacement $\mathbf{v}^*(\omega)$ on that same surface is computed as

$$v_{\text{RMS}}(\omega) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{R} \sum_{i=1}^R |v_i^*(\omega)|^2} \quad (29)$$

188 where R is the number of nodes of the model and $v_i^*(\omega)$ the response in the frequency domain of the
 189 i th node in the transverse direction.

190 4. Case studies

191 The presented methodology is then tested in Matlab for both beam and plates, for the FLD and
 192 CLD configurations in each case. For the sake of brevity, only the results for the simply supported case
 193 are reported, cantilever FLD and CLD beams are studied in [21,22] and the behaviour of FLD and CLD
 194 plates with different boundary conditions is analysed in [23,24].

The computations are done considering the density of the steel layers $\rho_1 = 7782 \text{ kg/m}^3$ and their Young's modulus $E_1 = 176.24 \text{ GPa}$. The viscoelastic layer has a density of $\rho_2 = 1423 \text{ kg/m}^3$ and a complex modulus that follows the four parameter fractional model

$$E_2^*(\omega) = \frac{E_r + E_u(i\omega\tau)^\alpha}{1 + (i\omega\tau)^\alpha} \quad (30)$$

195 in the frequency domain, where $E_r = 0.353 \text{ GPa}$ and $E_u = 3.462 \text{ GPa}$ are the relaxed and unrelaxed
 196 moduli respectively, $\tau = 314.9 \text{ }\mu\text{s}$ is the relaxation time and $\alpha = 0.873$ is the fractional parameter. These
 197 values are taken from the characterisation of the AISI T 316L stainless steel laminated sheet and the
 198 Soundown Vibration Damping Tile material performed in [27]. A value of 0.3 is considered for the
 199 Poisson's ratio of the steel and viscoelastic layers.

200 Three cases are studied for both FLD and CLD configurations, varying the thickness of the
 201 viscoelastic layer. For the FLD, the steel layer has a thickness $H_1 = 2 \text{ mm}$ and the thickness of the
 202 viscoelastic layer H_2 takes the value of 2 mm, 6 mm and 10 mm; for the CLD, the steel layers have a
 203 thickness $H_1 = H_3 = 1 \text{ mm}$ while the thickness of the viscoelastic layer H_2 can be 1 mm, 5 mm or
 204 10 mm. This ensures that the homogenised model is tested for both thin and thick structures.

205 4.1. Unconstrained layer damping (FLD)

206 4.1.1. FLD beams

207 To check the performance of the homogenised formulation for thin and thick viscoelastic layered
 208 beams, first a simply supported FLD beam 0.12 m long is considered, so that the thickness to length
 209 ratio is about 3 %, 5 % and 10 % when the viscoelastic layer has a thickness of 2 mm, 6 mm and 10 mm,
 210 respectively.

211 Two models are created: a 1D model based on beam elements with 2 DOF in each end (the
 212 transverse displacement v and the rotation θ_z , see Appendix A for the details) and a 3D model based
 213 on quadratic hexaedra with 27 nodes and 3 DOF in each node (the displacements u , v and w in the
 214 directions x , y and z , respectively). In the 1D model both the Oberst and the homogenised formulation
 215 are implemented, while the 3D model serves as the reference.

216 In order to ensure convergence for the first 10 modes, the 1D beam model is meshed with 60
 217 elements in its length and the 3D quadratic beam model has 4 elements in its width, 48 in its length
 218 and 2 in its height for each layer. This way, the beam model has 122 DOF while the solid model has
 219 23,571 DOF, roughly 200 times more, which has a direct impact on the computation time.

220 The simply supported boundary conditions are modelled differently depending on the model.
 221 For the 1D model, the transverse displacement of the two ends of the beam is blocked but the rotation
 222 is allowed. The 3D model requires additional considerations: the boundary conditions should be
 223 applied in the neutral fibre to allow the rotation of the section and the displacement in the direction
 224 of the beam should be allowed in one of the supports (Figure 3). As the position of the neutral fibre
 225 changes in frequency because damping makes it a complex magnitude, in this work, the decision to
 226 apply the boundary conditions in the middle of the section is taken. Given the stiffness of the beam,
 227 this simplification does not introduce a considerable error.

Figure 3. Boundary conditions of the solid beam. The dashed line represents the neutral fibre.

228 Table 1 shows the first three natural frequencies and loss factors for the three models and the
 229 three thickness cases analysed. Only the bending modes perpendicular to the beam are considered
 230 in the comparison, which are actually the ones that produce noise. In order to identify these mode
 231 shapes, the MAC value is used, which for mode shapes Φ_i and Φ_j takes the form

$$\text{MAC} = \frac{|\Phi_i^H \Phi_j|^2}{|\Phi_i^H \Phi_i| |\Phi_j^H \Phi_j|}, \quad (31)$$

232 where $(\bullet)^H$ stands for the Hermitian transpose.

H_2 (mm)	Mode	3D model		Homogenised model				Oberst model			
		ω (rad/s)	η	ω (rad/s)	Diff (%)	η	MAC	ω (rad/s)	Diff (%)	η	MAC
	1	1,813	0.0760	1,813	0.001	0.0765	1.00	1,814	0.05	0.0766	1.00
	2	7,578	0.0600	7,578	0.006	0.0602	1.00	7,596	0.24	0.0599	1.00
	3	17,201	0.0345	17,204	0.02	0.0348	1.00	17,299	0.57	0.0346	1.00
6	1	2,450	0.4472	2,453	0.25	0.4520	1.00	2,482	1.32	0.4502	1.00
	2	11,371	0.1839	11,467	0.87	0.1904	1.00	11,917	4.80	0.1819	1.00
	3	25,035	0.0953	25,369	1.33	0.1032	1.00	27,501	9.85	0.0930	1.00
10	1	4,013	0.4778	4,056	1.08	0.4916	1.00	4,208	4.86	0.4663	1.00
	2	16,683	0.1655	17,128	2.67	0.1818	1.00	19,204	15.1	0.1491	1.00
	3	33,861	0.0895	35,093	3.64	0.1096	1.00	43,905	29.7	0.0745	1.00

Table 1. Natural frequencies and loss factors of the simply supported FLD beam computed with the three models. For the beam models the percent difference in the natural frequencies and MAC value in comparison to the 3D model are shown.

233 The natural frequencies given by the homogenised formulation lie between the ones produced by
 234 the solids and those of the standard model. This means that the homogenised formulation is stiffer
 235 than the solid model because it does not introduce the in-plane displacement, but softer than the
 236 standard because the effect of shear is considered.

237 As expected, the Oberst method is accurate for the thinnest case producing results that diverge
 238 less than a 1 % from the reference model but starts to fall short when the thickness of the viscoelastic
 239 layer increases, specially for the third mode. The homogenised method, on the contrary, is able to
 240 accurately compute the natural frequencies of the FLD beam even for the greatest thickness, with a
 241 maximum divergence of less than 4 % from the values obtained with the solid model while the Oberst
 242 formulation presents a deviation of nearly 30 %.

243 Regarding the loss factor, the values of the loss factor are not directly comparable because of the
 244 differences in natural frequencies between the three models [22]. In fact, in this case the differences
 245 between the three models are minimal for the thinnest case but start growing together with thickness
 246 and mode number or, in other words, when the divergences in frequency increase.

247 On the subject of mode shapes, the standard and homogenised models produce, due to their
 248 formulation, the same eigenvectors and, thus, the MAC value for both models must be identical. In
 249 addition, both beam models are able to correctly reproduce the mode shapes of the reference model as
 250 the MAC value for every case is one.

251 As for the response, it is computed between 0 and 10 kHz and considering 500 samples in the
 252 frequency range so that the resolution is acceptable. Figure 4 shows the amplitude of the transverse
 253 displacement in frequency given by the three models for the three thickness cases studied. Due to the
 254 distributed pressure applied to the beam, only the symmetric modes appear in the response.

255 In view of the results, the main conclusion is that the homogenised model is able to reproduce the
 256 response obtained by the solid model in terms of amplitude and position of the resonant peaks for
 257 every case, while the Oberst formulation misses the highest frequency peak in the thick case.

Figure 4. Amplitude of the transverse displacement of the FLD beam when subjected to a unit pressure:
 (a) $H_2 = 2$ mm; (b) $H_2 = 6$ mm; (c) $H_2 = 10$ mm.

258 4.1.2. FLD plates

259 The homogenised formulation is then tested in a $0.1 \text{ m} \times 0.1 \text{ m}$ simply supported FLD plate.
 260 With this aim, a 2D model based on rectangular plate elements with 3 DOF in each node (the vertical
 261 displacement v and the rotations around the x and z axes θ_x and θ_z , (see Appendix A for the details)
 262 and a 3D model based in quadratic hexaedra are implemented. Both the Oberst and homogenised
 263 formulations are implemented in the 2D model.

264 The 3D model has 20 elements in each direction in the plane and two in the height in each
 265 layer, while the plate model has 50 elements in each direction in the plane. This mesh ensures the
 266 convergence of the first 10 modes for the three cases. In this case, the size of the problem is 8 times
 267 bigger for the solid model, with 65,559 DOF, than for the plate model, that only has 7,803 DOF.

268 The boundary conditions are applied in the four edges of the structure following the directions
 269 given in section 4.1.1: in the plate model, transverse displacement is blocked in the edges while
 270 rotations are allowed; in the solid model, boundary conditions are applied in the middle line of the
 271 cross section and in such a manner that the displacement in the plane of the plate is allowed.

272 The natural frequencies and loss factors of the FLD plate for the three different thicknesses are
 273 gathered in Table 2. The second mode is double because of the symmetry of the structure.

H_2 (mm)	Mode	3D model		Homogenised model			Oberst model				
		ω (rad/s)	η	ω (rad/s)	Diff (%)	η	MAC	ω (rad/s)	Diff (%)	η	MAC
2	1	5,631	0.0683	5,681	0.88	0.0692	0.95	5,691	1.07	0.0695	0.95
	2	14,318	0.0392	14,408	0.68	0.0397	-	14,477	1.11	0.0401	-
	3	22,837	0.0272	23,064	0.99	0.0277	0.80	23,242	1.77	0.0281	0.80
6	1	8,225	0.2326	8,565	4.14	0.2353	0.95	8,836	7.43	0.2273	0.95
	2	20,722	0.1110	21,383	3.17	0.1182	-	22,976	10.9	0.1079	-
	3	31,868	0.0754	33,182	4.12	0.0837	0.80	37,027	16.2	0.0725	0.80
10	1	12,072	0.2171	13,048	8.09	0.2223	0.95	14,334	18.7	0.1893	0.95
	2	28,186	0.1051	30,001	6.44	0.1299	-	36,725	30.3	0.0867	-
	3	41,125	0.0746	44,099	7.23	0.0949	0.80	59,023	43.5	0.0578	0.80

Table 2. Natural frequencies and loss factors of the simply supported FLD plate computed with the three models. For the plate models, the percent difference in frequency and MAC value in comparison to the 3D models is shown. MAC value is omitted for double modes.

274 Also in this case the differences in accuracy between the Oberst and the homogenised model
 275 when computing natural frequencies increase with the thickness of the viscoelastic layer, ranging from
 276 about 1 % for both models when $H_2 = 2$ mm to 43 % for the Oberst model and 7 % for the homogenised
 277 when $H_2 = 10$ mm and the highest natural frequency. This fact a consequence of the inclusion of the
 278 shear in the homogenised model, whose effect is more noticeable when the plate is thick.

279 On the subject of mode shapes, both the Oberst and the homogenised model are able to reproduce
 280 properly the results obtained in the reference model, taking into account the MAC values lie between
 281 0.8 and 0.95, the lower value being that of the mode of highest natural frequency. This difference can
 282 be attributed to the discretisation. MAC value is omitted in Table 2 for the second mode because, being
 283 a double mode, it is not applicable.

284 Regarding the response in the frequency domain, similar trends as the ones found when analysing
 285 FLD beams are observed (Figure 5): the homogenised formulation reproduces correctly the results
 286 given by the reference model while the Oberst model fails to predict the high frequency peak of the
 287 thick plate.

288 In view of the above, it can be concluded that the homogenised model offers a clear advantage
 289 when computing the natural frequencies, mode shapes and frequency response of FLD plates, taking
 290 into account that the obtained values are closer to the reference for the three thicknesses considered. In
 291 addition, it is even more cost-effective than the 3D solid model as it is capable of obtaining similar
 292 results at a reduced computation time because of its more limited size.

293 4.2. Constrained layer damping (CLD)

294 4.2.1. CLD beams

295 The structure under study in this case is a $L = 0.12$ m long simply supported CLD beam. As
 296 previously stated, three cases are analysed, varying the thickness of the viscoelastic layer (1 mm, 5 mm

Figure 5. Amplitude of the transverse displacement of a simply supported FLD plate when subjected to a unit pressure: (a) $H_2 = 2$ mm; (b) $H_2 = 6$ mm; (c) $H_2 = 10$ mm.

297 and 10 mm) while that of the metallic layers is kept constant. This allows to test the homogenised
 298 formulation for both thin and thick beams, as the thickness to length relationship ranges from 2.5 %,
 299 for the thin case, to 10 %, for the thick one.

300 A beam and a solid model are also developed for this case, both considering the same amount of
 301 nodes as the ones used to model FLD beam in section 4.1.1. The single difference is that for
 302 CLD structures the standard formulation is the RKU, that is included in Appendix B for the sake of
 303 completeness.

304 Boundary conditions are applied analogously as described when dealing with FLD plates: in the
 305 beam model, the transverse displacement is blocked in the two ends while the rotation is allowed;
 306 in the solid model, all displacements are blocked in the middle of the section in one end, while the
 307 displacement in the direction of the beam is allowed in the other.

308 The natural frequencies and loss factors computed by the three methods are shown in Table 3. In
 309 this case, the deviations in the natural frequencies are similar for the two beam models and range from
 310 less than 1 % for the thin beam to about 12 % for the thick beam and the highest natural frequency.

311 Even if the differences are not as high as in the previous cases, it is worth noting than the RKU model
 312 overestimates the natural frequencies because it overestimates the equivalent stiffness [28].

H_2 (mm)	Mode	3D model		Homogenised model				RKU model			
		ω (rad/s)	η	ω (rad/s)	Diff (%)	η	MAC	ω (rad/s)	Diff (%)	η	MAC
1	1	3,162	0.0337	3,165	0.12	0.0345	1.00	3,166	0.14	0.0340	1.00
	2	11,934	0.0379	11,959	0.21	0.0421	1.00	11,984	0.42	0.0407	1.00
	3	24,741	0.0370	24,752	0.05	0.0459	1.00	24,916	0.71	0.0429	1.00
5	1	7,185	0.0822	7,301	1.62	0.0869	1.00	7,283	1.36	0.0832	1.00
	2	22,746	0.0733	23,448	3.09	0.0953	1.00	23,474	3.20	0.0921	1.00
	3	40,341	0.0582	41,807	3.63	0.0928	0.99	42,105	4.37	0.0882	0.99
10	1	10,131	0.1096	10,707	5.69	0.1166	1.00	10,640	5.02	0.1099	1.00
	2	27,963	0.0846	30,743	9.95	0.1162	0.97	30,728	9.89	0.1124	0.97
	3	46,179	0.0654	51,473	11.5	0.1035	0.93	51,723	12.0	0.0998	0.93

Table 3. Natural frequencies and loss factors of the simply supported CLD beam computed with the three models. For the beam models the percent difference in the natural frequencies and MAC value with respect to the 3D model are also computed.

313 As for the mode shapes, the MAC value agrees for the RKU and homogenised formulations for all
 314 the thickness cases studied and its value decreases when the frequency of the mode increases. Apart
 315 from errors introduced by the discretisation, this is related to the coupling with bending in the other
 316 plane or the in-plane displacements, that are considered in the beam model and are more relevant
 317 when either the natural frequency or the thickness of the beam are higher.

318 As a final consideration regarding modes, it should be taken into account that, if the viscoelastic
 319 layer is thick, the bending modes in $x - z$ plane and the torsion modes appear at low frequency. As a
 320 beam model is not able to capture that behaviour, a plate model should be used instead.

321 Regarding the response, also in this case the divergences between the standard model and the
 322 homogenised formulation are more noticeable when either the frequency or the thickness of the
 323 viscoelastic layer increase. There is one aspect that is specific to CLD structures: the deviation of the
 324 natural frequencies computed by the homogenised formulation from those obtained by the reference
 325 3D model can be attributed to the coupling between in-plane and out-of-plane deformation, that is not
 326 included in the homogenised model.

327 In conclusion, the homogenised formulation outperforms the RKU for the three thickness cases
 328 under consideration, although the differences in performance are not as striking as in FLD beams
 329 because RKU was actually developed for simply supported CLD beams.

330 4.2.2. CLD plates

331 The last structure analysed is a $0.1 \text{ m} \times 0.1 \text{ m}$ CLD simply supported plate. Three cases are studied
 332 varying the thickness of the viscoelastic layer (1 mm, 5 mm and 10 mm) while the thickness of the
 333 metallic layers remains constant. The meshes and boundary conditions of the finite element beam and
 334 solid models are identical to those described for FLD plates in section 4.1.2.

335 The natural frequencies and loss factor for the simply supported CLD plate and the three values
 336 of thickness are shown in Tables 4. Also in this case the second mode is double due to the symmetry of
 337 the plate.

338 This is the case in which the homogenised model shows the greatest deviations in comparison to
 339 the reference, reaching a maximum error of 13 % for the third mode of the thick plate. Even in this
 340 case it is more accurate than the RKU that deviates about a 35 % from the reference model in the same
 341 conditions.

342 The differences between the two plate models are not so high if the mode shapes are studied,
 343 MAC values ranging around 0.75-0.95 for the cases in which it is applicable. Also in this case the MAC
 344 value decreases when the frequency increases for the reason described above.

Figure 6. Amplitude of the transverse displacement of the CLD beam when subjected to a unit pressure: (a) $H_2 = 1$ mm; (b) $H_2 = 5$ mm; (c) $H_2 = 10$ mm.

H_2 (mm)	Mode	3D model		Homogenised model			RKU model				
		ω (rad/s)	η	ω (rad/s)	Diff (%)	η	MAC	ω (rad/s)	Diff (%)	η	MAC
1	1	9,125	0.0554	9,162	0.41	0.0426	0.95	10,527	15.4	0.0337	0.95
	2	20,737	0.0420	21,103	1.76	0.0473	-	24,480	18.1	0.0364	-
	3	30,906	0.0393	31,459	1.36	0.0492	0.80	36,819	19.1	0.0368	0.80
5	1	17,786	0.0877	18,633	4.77	0.0987	0.95	21,692	22.0	0.0782	0.95
	2	34,684	0.0667	36,547	5.37	0.0977	-	43,215	24.6	0.0773	-
	3	47,244	0.0675	49,696	5.09	0.0929	0.78	59,319	25.6	0.0728	0.78
10	1	22,901	0.1040	24,930	12.0	0.1229	0.94	29,216	31.2	0.0979	0.94
	2	40,116	0.0739	45,397	13.5	0.1106	-	53,953	34.9	0.0893	-
	3	53,087	0.0608	59,928	13.0	0.0999	0.73	71,706	35.2	0.0805	0.73

Table 4. Natural frequencies and loss factors of the simply supported CLD plate computed with the three models. For the plate models, the percent difference in natural frequency and MAC values in comparison to the 3D model are shown. MAC value is omitted for double modes.

345 Concerning the response (Figure 7), the trends are similar to those found for the CLD beam:
 346 divergences in natural frequencies increase with thickness and frequency, being specially severe for
 347 the thick plate.

Figure 7. Amplitude of the transverse displacement of a CLD plate when subjected to a unit pressure:
 (a) $H_2 = 1$ mm; (b) $H_2 = 5$ mm; (c) $H_2 = 10$ mm.

348 It should be highlighted that the RKU is not able to reproduce the high frequency peak and
 349 presents accuracy problems for the second one even for the thin plate. The homogenised formulation,
 350 on the contrary, correctly reproduces the frequency response for the thin plate in terms of amplitude
 351 and frequency. When both the thickness and the frequency increase the deviation starts to be noticeable
 352 even for the homogenised formulation, specially regarding the amplitude. This is related to the
 353 contribution of coupled in-plane and out-of-plane motion, that is higher for CLD plates than for any of
 354 the structures analysed in this work.

$$\begin{aligned}
f_1 &= 10a^4 + 10b^4 + 7a^2b^2 - 2a^2b^2\nu \\
f_2 &= 10a^2 + b^2 + 4b^2\nu \\
f_3 &= 5a^2 + b^2 - b^2\nu \\
f_4 &= a^2 + 10b^2 + 4a^2\nu \\
f_5 &= a^2 + 5b^2 - a^2\nu \\
f_6 &= 5a^4 - 10b^4 - 7a^2b^2 + 2a^2b^2\nu \\
f_7 &= 5a^2 - b^2 - 4b^2\nu \\
f_8 &= a^2 + 10b^2 - a^2\nu \\
f_9 &= 5a^2 - 2b^2 + 2b^2\nu \\
f_{10} &= a^2 - 10b^2 - a^2\nu \\
f_{11} &= -5a^4 - 5b^4 + 7a^2b^2 - 2a^2b^2\nu \\
f_{12} &= 5a^2 - b^2 + b^2\nu \\
f_{13} &= -a^2 + 5b^2 + a^2\nu \\
f_{14} &= -10a^4 + 5b^4 - 7a^2b^2 + 2a^2b^2\nu \\
f_{15} &= 10a^2 - b^2\nu + b^2 \\
f_{16} &= a^2 - 5b^2 + 4a^2\nu \\
f_{17} &= 5a^2 - b^2 + b^2\nu \\
f_{18} &= 10a^2 - b^2 + b^2\nu \\
f_{19} &= -2a^2 + 5b^2 + 2a^2\nu
\end{aligned}$$

386 Appendix B. RKU formulation

387 The Ross, Kerwin and Ungar formulation defines the equivalent flexural stiffness for three layered
388 viscoelastic beams as

$$B_{\text{eq}}^* = (B_1 + B_3) \left(1 + \frac{X^*Y}{1 + X^*} \right) \quad (\text{A5})$$

389 the flexural stiffnesses for the i th layer being

$$B_i = \frac{E_i b H_i^3}{12} \quad (\text{A6})$$

390 and

$$X^* = \frac{G_2^* S}{k_B^2 H_2} \quad (\text{A7})$$

$$Y = \frac{12H_{31}^2}{S(E_1 H_1^3 + E_3 H_3^3)} \quad (\text{A8})$$

$$S = \frac{1}{E_1 H_1} + \frac{1}{E_3 H_3} \quad (\text{A9})$$

$$H_{31} = \frac{H_1 + H_3}{2} + H_2, \quad (\text{A10})$$

391 where H_i is the thickness of the i th layer and G_i its shear modulus. The variable k_B stands for the wave
392 number of the bending wave and its defined as

$$k_B = \sqrt[4]{\frac{\omega^2 \rho_L}{B_{eq}}}. \quad (\text{A11})$$

393 For plates, the flexural stiffness D_{eq} and the mass per unit area ρ_S should be used instead and, as
 394 the computations are done for unit width, $b = 1$ units of length (in the considered coherent system of
 395 units).

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